

Deviations from study protocol: “Training courses and materials for a research ethics and integrity informed green transition in Europe: a scoping review and gap analysis”

1. Additional authors

Joshua Gualtieri, Carly Seedall, Lisa Tambornino and François Jost contributed to the data collection. JG carried out searches and screened results. CG, LT and FJ screened results.

2. Changes to the original search strategy

Firstly, the original protocol stated that we would identify training materials and programmes by searching the websites of universities within the ERA and repositories/databases of training materials (search strategy 1) supplemented by a general web search (search strategy 2). Instead of the general web search, which was too broad and returned almost completely irrelevant results, we performed country-specific Google web searches for each ERA country.

Secondly, we made changes to the search of university websites. Due to restrictions on the number of search terms that can be included in queries used in Google, we split our search terms across 2 queries. Additionally, in order to make this search more manageable, we divided the 460 websites to be screened into 5 batches. Taken together, these changes meant that 10 separate searches were conducted (search query 1 x 5 batches of uni websites, search query 2 x 5 batches of uni websites).

Thirdly, after assessing the quality of the results returned by our chosen search engines - Bing and Google - we decided to only use Google for all searches as the results returned were more relevant and reliable. Similarly, we reduced the limit on the number of results returned per university website from 100 to 30 after preliminary screening indicated that few relevant results were returned above this limit.

Appendix B presents all details of the amended search strategy.

3. Refinement of inclusion and exclusion criteria for training materials and programmes

Refinements were made to some inclusion and exclusion criteria following the comparison between the first and second screeners' inclusion decisions for the country-specific web searches. These minor amendments, relating to the time frame, access and content requirements, specify more precisely which results are considered relevant and are detailed in **Appendix A.2**.

4. Changes to data analysis plan

To ensure continuity between tasks within the work package in which this study is conducted, materials created in other tasks within the work package will be used for the

qualitative content analysis of included training materials and programmes. Namely, a framework of preliminary findings from the conceptual review [protocol available here: [Core concepts and issues in research ethics and integrity, climate ethics, and environmental ethics, in the context of research and innovation: a scoping review protocol \(zenodo.org\)](#)] and a framework of technologies and values relevant to research integrity and ethics in the context of the green transition.